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Use of Innovative Technologies in Preschool Educational Organizations

Tursunova Sarvinoz Fazliddinovna

Shahrisabz State Institute of Pedagogy Faculty of Pedagogy Pre-school education 3rd grade student

Abstract: *This article examines the use of innovative technologies in preschool educational organizations. How technologies such as interactivity, creativity, flexibility and visualization affect the intellectual, social and emotional development of children are analyzed. Also, methods of using technologies such as digital games, interactive whiteboards, virtual reality and robotics in preschool education are presented.*

Key words: *innovative technologies, preschool education, interactive boards, digital games, robotics, visualization.*

Introduction: The modern educational process is developing rapidly, and the integration of new technologies into education is becoming one of the most urgent issues today. In particular, the use of innovative technologies in preschool educational organizations has a great impact on the intellectual, social and emotional development of children. This article talks about the importance of innovative technologies in the preschool education system, their advantages and methods of practical use. Innovative technologies mean the integration of new, modern software and hardware tools into the educational process.

These technologies provide children with opportunities to learn in an interactive environment and play an important role in attracting their attention and increasing their interest. Based on the specific characteristics of education for preschool children, it is necessary to choose innovative methods suitable for them.

Discussion and results: The advantages of innovative technologies in preschool education are many.

1. **Interactivity:** With the help of interactive technologies, children receive information more easily and participate with more interest. For example, electronic boards, multimedia applications and gaming platforms attract children's attention and develop their creativity.
2. **Adaptability:** Innovative technologies allow to adapt the educational process to each child individually. This helps in the learning process and helps in working with students of different

levels.

3. Creativity and problem solving: Through innovative technologies, children are given the skills to solve various problems with their own independent thoughts. With the help of these technologies, children learn to solve problems in real situations.
4. Visualization: Visual education is very effective for children because it develops their logical and imaginative thinking. For example, it is possible to show children the scenery of the world and explain natural phenomena through virtual reality technologies.

The methods of using innovative technologies in preschool education include:

1. Digital games: Children find it easy to learn through play. Through programs, mobile applications or computer games, they can learn colors, shapes, numbers and other basic knowledge. For example, through construction games like LEGO, children develop creativity and logical thinking skills.
2. Interactive whiteboards: Electronic whiteboards enhance communication with students because they can actively participate in the lesson. With the help of digital content, there will be an opportunity to explain various topics and conduct live classes for children.
3. Virtual and Augmented Reality: These technologies are very useful for expanding children's knowledge and developing their worldview. For example, through VR glasses, children can travel to unfamiliar places or see historical events.
4. Robotics: Children's interest in technology and their management skills are formed through robotics programs in preschool education. This will serve to prepare for learning in the technological fields in the future.

Conclusion: The use of innovative technologies in the preschool education system has a positive effect on the development of children. Through interactive, creative and flexible learning methods, children not only learn, but also develop their abilities. Therefore, the widespread introduction of innovative technologies in preschool educational organizations is the need of the hour. By effectively using the possibilities of these technologies, it is possible to increase the interest and motivation of children in the educational process.

List of used literature:

1. Azizkhojayev A.A., Nasirov Z.Kh. Modern technologies in education. Tashkent: National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, 2020.
2. Kholmukhamedov S.H. Innovative methods and technologies in preschool education. Tashkent: Sharq NMAK, 2019.
3. Smirnova E.O., Kotova I.N. Инновационные технологии в дошкольном образовании. Москва: Академия, 2018.
4. Papert, S. Mindstorms: Children, Computers, and Powerful Ideas. New York: Basic Books, 1980.
5. Mishra, P., & Koehler, M. J. Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge: A Framework for Teacher Knowledge. Teachers College Record, 2006.
6. Goncharova, N. I., Использование инновационных технологий в дошкольном обучении. Вопросы образования и науки, 2017.
7. Johnson, L., Becker, S.A., Estrada, V., & Freeman, A. NMC Horizon Report: 2015 K–12 Edition.

The New Media Consortium, 2015.

8. Virtual Reality Society. Applications of Virtual Reality in Education.
<https://www.vrs.org.uk/virtual-reality-education>, 2020.